

Overall study design

Title of the study	Lipid profiling of liver tissue isolated from Cox14 KO mice vs WT control.		
Document creation date	03/28/2024	Corresponding Email	britta.bruegger@bzh.uni-heidelberg.de
Principle investigator	Britta Brügger / Heidelberg Lipidomics Platform	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted
Institution	Heidelberg University Biochemistry Center	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	2-phase system	Bligh&Dyer
Derivatization	-	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	Hydrochloric acid		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS1	3.3
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Profile mode
MS type	Orbitrap	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
MS vendor	Thermo	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
Direct type	Chip	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	70000
MS Level	MS1, MS2	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	4
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	High resolution	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
Resolution at m/z 200 at MS1	140000	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Solvent blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification and identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	mtbls9823	Raw data upload	No
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

WT isolated liver tissue flash frozen in liquid nitrogen / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Sample homogenization	Yes
Storage time (month)	0.5	Sample homogenization solvent	Methanol
Freeze-thaw cycles	2		

COX14 isolated liver tissue flash frozen in liquid nitrogen / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Sample homogenization	Yes
Storage time (month)	0	Sample homogenization solvent	Methanol
Freeze-thaw cycles	2		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Which assumptions were presumed?	LipidXplorer MFQL accounts for fatty acid chain length of 14 to 22
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction, Thermo .raw file conversion and SIM stitching by Peakstrainer to centroided mzXML file
Fragment name -FA1(-H)-(H2O+NH3) -FA2(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

1) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard Endogenous subclass DG DG 17:0/17:0			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

2) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Which assumptions were presumed?	LipidXplorer MFQL accounts for fatty acid chain length of 12 to 22
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction, Thermo .raw file conversion and SIM stitching by Peakstrainer to centroided mzXML file
Fragment name			
-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA2(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA3(+HO)-(NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

2) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
TG	d5-TG 14:0_14:0_16:1		
TG	d5-TG 15:0_15:0_18:1		
TG	d5-TG 17:1_17:0_17:0		
TG	d5-TG 18:2_20:4_20:4		
TG	d5-TG 18:3_20:2_20:2		
TG	d5-TG 22:6_20:5_20:5		
TG	d5-TG 20:1_20:0_20:0		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		